

Per Anhalter durch das Immunsystem

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Keywords

Biology, Health, Immunology, Medicine, Nutritional Science, Physiological Systems

Introduction

Per Anhalter durch das Immunsystem is a digital educational game designed to support the teaching and learning of immunological processes for students of life sciences. It was published in 2024 by Christian Zimmermann, a scientist and lecturer in nutritional sciences at Justus Liebig University Giessen. The game was developed in collaboration with students and HessenHub, the Network for Digital University Teaching in Hesse, in Giessen. The goal of the game is to teach students how specific processes in the immune system work. It is designed as a point-and-click adventure in a simplified cartoon style, where players interact with immune cells and complete various tasks. In the game, players must prepare for an attack by pathogens and respond by producing specific antibodies. Through this process, they gain insights into how immune cells interact and how immune responses occur. Throughout the game, the players are required to solve puzzles and reflect on the content they have learned.

Facts

Release date:	2024
Developer:	Christian Zimmermann, HessenHub Giessen
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	Single player
Format:	Asynchronous
Time frame:	20–40 minutes
Languages:	German
Environment:	Browser-enabled device with internet connection
Material:	Digital device
Price:	Free of charge

Resonance & Criticism

So far, the game has received little response since its recent release. Initial evaluations from students who participated in a module on basic immunology show a high acceptance rate and positive feedback regarding the game's educational impact. In line with the feedback, the game's design increased learning motivation and encouraged active engagement with the

content. All previous surveys on this game showed that the participants in the evaluation regarded learning games as applicable in this subject-specific context. Based on content-related questions about the interaction of immune cells in response to an antigen included in the assessment, a learning effect could be confirmed.

Game Principle & Process

Figure 1. Screenshot from *Per Anhalter durch das Immunsystem* (Zimmermann; HessenHub Gießen). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Per Anhalter durch das Immunsystem is a digital serious game based on the principles of a point-and-click adventure. Set in a simplified, cartoon-style science fiction environment, players encounter pathogens that must be analyzed and processed by immune cells. Players are introduced to the game mechanics by an anthropomorphized cell, which also serves as their guide throughout the game. The goal is to prepare for an impending infection by producing antibodies to neutralize the pathogens. Throughout the game, players must repeatedly decide how different immune cells interact. They receive guidance on the correct choices through interactions with the cells. Additionally, the ongoing processes are explained with supplementary information. If players are unsure of what to do, a help menu is available for support. As players progress through the game, they learn about the development of B memory cells and antibody-producing plasma cells, as well as other cells involved in this

process. The narrative-driven format combines educational content with gamified elements to increase engagement.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Per Anhalter durch das Immunsystem places immunological processes, which are usually only presented schematically in textbooks, into an interactive and playful context where students can actively experience the content. To facilitate the understanding of key immunological aspects and the overall immunological concept, the game relies on simplification.

Students can first play the game independently as part of a self-learning phase or use it as a review tool for content from a previous lecture. By incorporating puzzles into the game, both critical thinking and decision-making skills are encouraged (Fotaris & Mastoras, 2019). Additionally, the understanding of facts is deepened by requiring players to apply the integrated knowledge within the game to solve problems (Hense & Mandl, 2012). The game design allows students to engage with the material at their own pace, accommodating individual learning needs. In a safe learning environment, they can make mistakes and learn from them without fear of evaluation or pressure (Fischer et al., 2017).

In a complementary lecture or seminar, instructors can then explore specific aspects in more detail or supplement them with additional information that is presented in a simplified form within the game.

Effectiveness

There are no studies on this game, and therefore, no empirical findings so far.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

To play the game, players need an internet-enabled device. Without an internet connection, the game cannot be played. Because of its visual design, the game may be unsuitable for individuals with visual impairments. Players should also have basic immunological knowledge, as otherwise they may find it difficult to navigate within the game world. Because the game simplifies immunological concepts, there is a risk that some ideas may be misunderstood if it is played without further explanation.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl

Sources

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